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1. Glossary

SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
AU	African Union
EU	European Union
OSeMOSYS	Open Source Energy Modelling System
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
CMP	Continental Master Plan (Africa)
AfSEM	African Single Electricity Market
GW	Gigawatt
NDCs	Nationally Determined Contributions
NECPs	National Energy and Climate Plans
AEEP	Africa-EU Energy Partnership
MARKAL	Market Allocation model
MESSAGE	Model for Energy Supply Strategy Alternatives and their General Environmental Impact
TIMES	The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System
TEMBA	The Electricity Model Base for Africa
OSEMBE	Open-Source energy Model Base for Europe
GENeSYS-MOD	Global Energy System Model
TIAM-ECN	TIMES Integrated Assessment Model (Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands)
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
AETOS	Africa-Europe Energy Transition OSeMOSYS model
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
MtCO ₂ -eq	Million tonnes of CO ₂ equivalent
PJ	Petajoule
Kt	Kilotonne

CHP	Combined Heat and Power
JRC-IDEES	Joint Research Centre - Integrated Database of the European Energy System
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
PRIS	Power Reactor Information System (IAEA)
TYNDP	Ten-Year Network Development Plan
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
ENTSO-G	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas
TAP	Trans Adriatic Pipeline
TANAP	Trans-Anatolian Natural Gas Pipeline
STEPS	Stated Policies Scenario (IEA)
HFO	Heavy Fuel Oil
EBA	European Biogas Association
HICP	Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (EU)
CPI-U	Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers (US)
IEA	International Energy Agency
CFs	Capacity Factors
VRE	Variable Renewable Energy
PV	Photovoltaic
MERRA-2	Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2
PLEXOS	Plexus Optimisation and Simulation
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
CEER	European Energy Regulators
EIA	Energy Information Administration
ETS	Emissions Trading System
WEM	With Existing Measures
WAM	With Additional Measures
BS	Baseline
BSNZ	Baseline Net-Zero

PN	Planned
PNNZ	Planned Net-Zero
UN	Unrestricted
UNNZ	Unrestricted Net-Zero
N/A	Not Applicable
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
LFO	Light Fuel Oil
TWh	Terawatt-hour
EL	Electricity
NG	Natural Gas
PP	Power Plant
T	Transmission
D	Distribution
CAR	Central African Republic

Abstract

The global energy landscape is rapidly evolving towards a low-carbon future, driven by commitments under the Paris Agreement and other key initiatives like the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the Green Climate Fund, and national decarbonization pledges. Within this context, the African Union (AU), characterized by growing energy markets and abundant resources, together with the European Union (EU), leveraging its technological expertise and investment capacity, are uniquely positioned to forge a transformative energy partnership. Despite the shared decarbonisation goal, collaboration has not yet fully capitalised on their complementary strengths. Furthermore, the lack of robust scientific insights limits policymakers' and investors' ability to develop effective strategies. This work aims to identify opportunities for a balanced and mutually beneficial energy partnership that supports decarbonisation efforts across both continents. A model representing the national electricity supply system of forty-eight African nations and thirty European countries is developed in a cost-optimisation modelling framework (OSeMOSYS). This model facilitates the analysis of cost-optimal energy pathways under varying scenarios of enhanced interregional connectivity, emphasizing the development of gas trade infrastructure and electricity grid interconnections. Results from this analysis provide insights into the benefits and trade-offs of enhanced trade collaboration. Key findings include investment requirements, technology and energy mix, as well as Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emission projections across a range of scenarios.

Keywords: electricity trade; natural gas infrastructure; cost-optimisation; decarbonisation

1. Introduction

The transition to low-carbon energy systems is gaining momentum, driven by international agreements such as the Paris Agreement and coordinated through national and regional initiatives. These efforts have accelerated renewable energy deployment in the power sector. However, despite these commitments, the energy transition remains off track with studies indicating the need to triple the current capacity of renewable energy technologies to meet global climate targets [1].

Africa's ambition is evident, making significant strides towards low-carbon development pathways, complementing its efforts to expand energy access, while simultaneously addressing climate change. This commitment has been conveyed through two flagship initiatives: the Continental Master Plan (CMP) [2] and the Africa Single Electricity Market (AfSEM) [3]. Together, these initiatives aim to boost the continent's renewable energy capacity by 300 GW by 2030 and 760 GW by 2040. This transition aligns with national and regional frameworks such as Agenda 2063 [4] and the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) [5]. Despite ongoing planning, the continent faces significant energy access deficit with three-quarters of the population lacking electricity access, resulting from insufficient investment as the continent receives only 2% of global investments in clean energy over the last two decades [6], while it corresponds to 18.3% of the world's population. This is due to the fact that investors are often discouraged by inefficient bureaucracies, limited energy expertise, and elevated risks of corruption and contractual issues compared to other markets [7].

In parallel, Europe has established ambitious climate goals, through the European Green Deal regional initiative, aiming to cut net greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels and to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 [8]. Comprehensive strategic planning tools such as the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) [9] are enforced and required by the EU law, mandated under the Governance of the Energy Unions and Climate Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 to drive the energy transition. Early assessments and reports indicate that significant progress has been made in energy security, renewable adoption, and emissions reduction, showcasing resilience in overcoming unprecedented challenges. However, achieving 2030 and 2050 targets will require stronger coordination, increased investments in clean technologies, and sustained efforts to ensure a sustainable and competitive energy future [10].

Amid both continents' effort for decarbonization, research into energy cooperation between Africa and Europe remains limited. While initiatives like the Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP) [11] focus on expanding sustainable energy access in Africa, comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and complexities involved in energy exchange between the African Union and European Union remains limited. In particular, a deeper exploration of the benefits and feasibility of establishing a transcontinental energy trade network is lacking. Although efforts to bridge this knowledge gap are ongoing, much remains to be explored regarding the technical, economic, and geopolitical implications of such a partnership.

In this context, energy system modelling serves as a critical framework for understanding and planning complex energy systems, enabling stakeholders to evaluate the impacts of technological advancements, policy changes, and market dynamics [12]. By representing the interactions between supply, demand, infrastructure, and emissions, energy models provide quantitative insights to guide strategic decisions toward sustainable and reliable energy futures.

Several studies have addressed the potential for energy trade between different regions. Over the years, a range of specialized models, primarily cost-optimisation model, have been developed to address the complex challenges related to long-term energy planning. Notable examples among these are MARKAL [13], MESSAGE [14], TIMES [15], and OSeMOSYS [16], each offering unique strengths in

capturing the dynamic interplay between energy supply, demand, and policy interventions across different timeframes and geographic scales. These models have become essential tools for decision-makers in shaping sustainable, resilient energy futures by simulating the effects of various technological, economic, and policy scenarios.

The OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) [16] framework has been frequently adopted to address energy planning and policy analysis worldwide. In Africa, models like TEMBA (The Electricity Model Base for Africa) [17] have provided insights into the benefits of regional energy integration, although these studies largely focus on internal energy developments without fully exploring potential trade with Europe. Similarly, the OSEMBE (Open Source Electricity Model Base for Europe) [18] model has provided extensive insights on the European energy system but has not adequately incorporated external linkages, particularly in relation to Africa. Another study by Taliotis et al. explored enhancing decarbonization in power generation through electricity trade in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East regions, linking the eastern flank of the EU to Egypt [19].

Building on these efforts, several researchers and organizations have developed models to represent the global energy system [20]. For example, Barnes et al. introduced OSeMOSYS Global, which allows for flexible configuration of both spatial resolution (up to 163 countries and 265 nodes) and temporal resolution [16]. Similarly, Löffler et al. utilized GENeSYS-MOD, dividing the world into geographical clusters (i.e. Africa, China, Europe, Former Soviet Union, India, etc.) [22]. Another notable model is TIAM-ECN, developed by TNO Energy Transition, which disaggregates the global system into 36 regions, enabling region-specific analysis [23]. However, many of these models rely on aggregated data and operate at lower temporal resolutions, limiting their ability to capture more detailed dynamics. As a result, despite significant progress, the research landscape remains fragmented, emphasizing the need for more comprehensive studies to fully understand and model transcontinental energy networks.

To address this gap in the literature, this study develops the first fully open-source, high-resolution energy systems model that explicitly represents electricity and natural gas interconnections between Africa and Europe. By capturing cross-continental infrastructure and trade flows at the country level, the model enables a detailed assessment of the feasibility and system-wide impacts of enhanced AU-EU energy cooperation.

The first section sets the context and highlights the relevance of energy cooperation between the two continents. The second section introduces the methodological approach, detailing the model structure, input data, and key assumptions. Section 3 presents the results of the analysis and provides a critical discussion of their implications. The final section summarizes the key insights and outlines directions for future research and model refinement.

2. Methods

2.1. Modelling methodology

The AETOS (Africa-Europe energy Transition OSeMOSYS) model developed in this paper adopts the OSeMOSYS modelling framework – an open-source, bottom-up, energy system optimization tool used for national, regional, and global analyses [24], [25], [26]. It is suitable for the evaluation of long-term energy planning scenarios. Its transparency and modular structure make it well-suited for long-term planning and for capturing the complexities of transcontinental energy systems. OSeMOSYS operates by minimising the total discounted system cost, meaning that it identifies the most cost-effective configuration for the entire modelled region, rather than optimising each national system independently. As a result, investment decisions may be concentrated in countries with the most competitive energy resources—such as those with abundant low-cost renewables—with electricity then exported to neighbouring systems. This enables lower-cost supply for importing regions compared to domestic alternatives. Furthermore, the model can represent trade flows that balance generation surpluses or deficits across the interconnected network, such as exporting excess electricity during low demand or meeting peak demand shortfalls elsewhere. In this way, cross-border trade supports deferred investments and improved system-wide efficiency.

The model considers a range of assumptions, including final energy demand, existing and planned power infrastructure, trade infrastructure, projected technoeconomic characteristics, fuel price trajectories, fossil fuel reserves, renewable resource availability, and national energy and climate policy targets.

The principal outputs generated by the model include technology-specific electricity generation and associated capacity expansion over time, cross-border trade flows and net imports/exports, total system costs and their breakdown (Capital, Fixed and Variable Operation & Maintenance (O&M), Fuel, Emission costs), greenhouse gas emissions by fuel type, and resource use (i.e., fuel extraction or renewable energy utilisation). These outputs are reported annually for each country and for the aggregated system, enabling the comparative assessment of scenarios in terms of cost, emissions, and trade dynamics. A summary of the key AETOS model inputs and outputs is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Key inputs and outputs in AETOS model.

This study utilizes the established OSeMOSYS regional models for Europe (OSeMBE) [27] and Africa (TEMBA) [28], [29]; these two continental models are updated and combined to form the AETOS model. In both frameworks, each country is modelled as an independent energy system capable of trading electricity and gas through existing and planned infrastructure such as interconnectors and pipelines. A reference energy system (RES) structure is developed to represent each national system uniformly for each continent (Appendix A). Technology representation is country-specific—technologies such as nuclear or hydropower are only included where relevant, based on existing or planned capacities.

Table 1. Summary of updates to OSeMBE and TEMBA.

Parameter	OSeMBE (EU)	TEMBA (AU)
Demand Profiles (Timeslices)	4 seasons × 4 dayparts = 16 timeslices	4 seasons × 4 dayparts = 16 timeslices
New Generation Technologies	Derived gas, refinery gas, diesel, lignite, CCS (natural gas & biomass)	CCS (natural gas, biomass, and coal), enabled NG technologies investment regardless of existing capacity, expanded wind/solar options by country.
Storage Technologies	Pumped hydro and batteries added	Pumped hydro and batteries added
Fuel Prices	Harmonized	Harmonized
Emission Factors	Updated (Mt CO ₂ eq/PJ and kt/PJ for CO ₂)	Updated (Mt CO ₂ eq/PJ and kt/PJ for CO ₂)
Technology Classification	Categorized as Old, New, and CCS for natural gas and biomass; coal excluded	Same categories used; coal retained
Technology Aggregation	Simplified to one CHP and one electricity-only technology per fuel	Aggregated sub-technologies by fuel
Capacity Factors	Updated for wind, solar, and hydro	Updated for wind, solar, and hydro
Annual Representation	2021–2055	2021–2055
Cost definitions	Updated to US\$2021	Updated to US\$2021
Annual Electricity Demand	Updated	Updated
Annual Gas Demand (except electricity production)	Added	Added
Residuals and Committed Capacities	Updated	Updated
Transmission/Distribution Losses	Disaggregated into transmission (E1) and distribution (E2); updated values	Same approach applied
Extraction/Import Technologies	Imports and extractions separated for fossil fuels	Imports and extractions separated for fossil fuels

OSeMBE and TEMBA are independently updated to reflect the latest available data and to harmonize model structures and assumptions. Key structural adjustments include the enhancement of the

temporal resolution, now aligned across both models with four seasons and four dayparts (16 timeslices). For the European energy system, additional components are integrated, including battery storage technologies, carbon capture and storage (CCS) options for fossil fuels and biomass, and expanded gas infrastructure. Similarly, battery storage technologies are also added to the African energy system. These updates aim to improve the representation of power sector flexibility and emissions mitigation potential.

The overarching objective of this work is to systematically update and align the two models prior to their eventual integration into a unified Europe-Africa system model. This integration seeks to improve the representation of intercontinental energy trade and to eliminate cross-model inconsistencies. A detailed summary of the parameter-level updates to OSeMBE and TEMBA is provided in Table 1.

2.2. Key input data and assumptions

Given the limited direct engagement with national authorities and utilities in both continents, the model relies primarily on data obtained from publicly accessible sources. This section outlines the key input data and the assumptions supporting the analysis. Where relevant, model-specific differences between Europe and Africa are highlighted, reflecting regional policy contexts, resource endowments, and data availability.

2.2.1. Generation Technologies

The models represent a portfolio of power generation technologies reflecting both existing infrastructure and future investment options. These include thermal (coal, gas, oil), nuclear, hydropower, biomass and variable renewable energy technologies (wind, solar).

For Europe, a more detailed representation of technologies was initially present, however, for consistency and model tractability, generation technologies are aggregated into a simplified structure that includes one combined heat and power (CHP) and one or two electricity-generating technologies per fuel each with an “existing” and “future” variant. Existing technologies represent installed capacity until its eventual decommissioning, while only new investments in advanced technologies are permitted from 2023 onwards. Certain technologies such as nuclear, coal, lignite and hydropower are only included in countries which have existing capacities or planned investments. New technologies such as CCS-enabled natural gas and biomass are introduced. For EU countries existing infrastructure, detailed data of capacities including decommissioning capacities and some investments are sourced from JRC-IDEES-2021 [30]. For Norway, Switzerland and United Kingdom, data are derived from IRENA Statistics 2025 [31].

Representation of African electricity supply systems, follows a comparable methodology, using IRENA Statistics 2025 [31] from 2021–2024 for existing capacity inputs, including both off-grid (e.g. mini-grids, standalone systems) and on-grid infrastructure. Bio-related technologies, including bagasse, wood waste etc., are aggregated into a single “biomass” category for clarity. New technologies, including CCS-enabled natural gas, biomass and coal are integrated. A detailed table of all technologies and their existing capacities can be found in the supplementary material.

Future investments in generation infrastructure are a critical aspect, given the evolving nature of national strategies. To address this, investments are categorized into “committed”—i.e., those expected to occur—and “candidate”— i.e., those that might occur. For Europe, technology investments that are considered more certain, such as nuclear and hydropower, are sourced from PRIS [32] and the Global Energy Monitor Hydropower Tracker [33] database; these are classified as committed. Other planned additions, including wind and solar, are derived from EU member states’ National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) [9] and treated as candidate investments. For Africa, investment assumptions are primarily based on the African Continental Master Plan (CMP) [2].

Similarly, nuclear and hydropower projects listed in PRIS [32] and the Global Energy Monitor [33] are treated as “committed”, while other planned additions followed the “candidate” classification, based on their status in national and regional planning documents. A table with these capacities can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2.2. Storage Technologies

Storage technologies are integrated and represented in the models to capture their critical role in enabling flexibility and supporting variable renewable energy integration. The current model structure includes two types of energy storage, battery storage and pumped hydro storage. Battery storage is modelled as a short-duration (4-hour), fast-response technology suitable for daily balancing, while pumped hydro provides longer-duration storage (8-hour) with large-scale capacity. Where applicable, storage capacities are derived from existing infrastructure databases and complemented by projected investments from regional planning documents.

For Europe, existing pumped storage capacity data are sourced from JRC-IDEES-2021 [30], while planned infrastructures are taken from TYNDP 2024 [34]. Battery storage existing capacities are based on the Eurostat database [35], while planned infrastructures are derived from the NECPs of each country [9]. For Africa, existing capacities for both battery and pumped storage are derived from the CMP [2] along with some battery deployment projections. Planned pumped hydro capacities are drawn from the Global Energy Monitor [33]. More detail on these storage capacities can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2.3. Grid Interconnections

Representation of grid interconnections in Europe is based on a combination of existing, planned and candidate infrastructure. Existing cross-border transmission links are sourced from the original OSeMBE model [18] and European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) Transparency Platform [36], while planned and candidate interconnectors are drawn from the ENTSO-E’s TYNDP 2024 and 2026 [37][38]. All identified Europe–Africa interconnections in TYNDP are explicitly included and flagged for integration. Line lengths have been recorded for each interconnector to facilitate the calculation of associated capital and operational expenditures. Where possible, values have been cross-validated using multiple sources, including National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) [9], which are systematically reviewed for all EU Member States. For cases where complete data is unavailable, own estimates are used. A symmetric exchange capacity is assumed for all modelled interconnectors, which means that bidirectional electricity flow is allowed at equal capacities.

Similarly, in Africa, existing, planned and candidate interconnections are adopted from the JRC TEMBA model [39], which forms the structural foundation for electricity trade representation. These were cross-validated and complemented with additional transmission corridors identified in the Africa Continental Master Plan (CMP) [2], thereby enhancing regional connectivity assumptions. Europe–Africa interconnectors from TYNDP 2024 and 2026 [37], [38] have also been incorporated and appropriately flagged within the African model framework.

In both Africa and Europe, interconnections with countries beyond the model boundaries such as Russia, Turkey, and Jordan, have also been explicitly represented to capture regional electricity exchanges more comprehensively.

Detailed data on grid interconnector capacities can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2.4. Natural Gas Pipeline Network and LNG Infrastructure

The natural gas network in the AETOS model includes cross-border pipeline infrastructure, liquefied natural gas (LNG) terminals (i.e., liquefaction and regasification facilities), and natural gas production capacity, capturing the full spectrum of natural gas supply infrastructure.

For the European system (OSeMBE), existing and planned pipeline infrastructure is sourced from the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas (ENTSO-G) [40] and the original OSeMBE dataset [18]. Planned projects are categorized into three expansion scenarios: Low, Advanced, and High, which are cross-validated using national NECPs, wherever data is available. Major cross-border pipelines from non-EU countries to EU-countries such as the Trans Adriatic Pipeline (TAP) and Trans-Anatolian Natural Gas Pipeline (TANAP), which include transit countries like Turkey and Albania, are explicitly modelled without detailed representation of the energy system of these countries. LNG import and export terminals are incorporated based on the Global Energy Monitor Infrastructure Gas Tracker [41], distinguishing between existing and planned facilities. Details regarding natural gas extraction are provided in Section 2.2.9.

For the African system (TEMBA), existing pipelines are based on the original TEMBA dataset [39] and expanded using information from the Africa Continental Master Plan (CMP). Existing intra-African pipelines are well captured, while planned infrastructure is classified as committed, or candidate, depending on development status. LNG infrastructure, specifically liquefaction and regasification capacities and proposed expansions, is similarly sourced from the Global Energy Monitor Gas Tracker [41].

All intercontinental pipelines between Europe and Africa such as the Algeria-Italy and Algeria-Spain gas routes are explicitly represented. All cross-border pipelines—including intra-European, intra-African, and intercontinental links—are modelled with asymmetric flow assumptions to reflect potential trade imbalances and infrastructure limitations. In cases of missing data, conservative and transparent assumptions are applied and clearly documented.

Information on the natural gas trade capacities can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2.5. Fuel Prices and Technoeconomic Parameters

Fossil fuel price assumptions are critical in shaping the cost-optimal energy mix across interconnected regions. In this study, a harmonised pricing approach is adopted for most fuels to ensure comparability between the European and African contexts. This decision is motivated by the objective to evaluate technology competitiveness under equal market conditions, without introducing distortions from regional or national price subsidies or trade imbalances.

To that end, crude oil, natural gas, and coal prices projections are taken from the IEA World Energy Outlook 2024 under the EU Stated Policies Scenario (STEPS) [42], selected for its conservative outlook and long-term internal consistency. LNG import prices are adopted based on the STEPS- Japan natural gas projections, since supply in these regions is exclusively via LNG terminals. Lignite prices are assumed to be 20% cheaper than coal, reflecting their lower energy content and marginal extraction costs. For diesel and heavy fuel oil (HFO), price trajectories are derived as fixed percentages of the crude oil price based on relevant IRENA regional analyses [43], and adjusted annually in line with STEPS crude oil projections. Uranium prices are also based on IRENA assumptions [43]. Biomass prices are sourced from the BaltPool exchange [44], while biogas prices are taken from the European Biogas Association (EBA) [45].

The technoeconomic parameters of generation and storage technologies, including capital cost, fixed and variable O&M, and efficiencies, are compiled from multiple sources to reflect regionally-

consistent and policy-relevant assumptions. Primary sources include the EU Reference Scenario 2020 [46] and existing datasets from OSeMBE [18] and TEMBA [39]. Pumped hydro storage costs are disaggregated into power capacity and energy storage components. Similarly, battery storage systems are disaggregated into energy storage and inverter components, reflecting distinct cost drivers [47]

Finally, the costs of regional electricity interconnections are estimated using distance-based and capacity tiers cost assumptions derived from other infrastructure planning studies [48]. This allows the endogenous selection of interconnection capacity in scenarios involving transcontinental electricity or gas trade. For gas pipelines and LNG terminals, cost assumptions are derived from relevant studies [49]. All cost definitions are converted to 2021 USD using the average annual exchange rate from the European Central Bank (4 Jan–31 Dec 2021) [50], the EU Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (HICP) [51], and the U.S. CPI-U (average of HALF1 and HALF2) from the Bureau of Labor Statistics [52]. Table 2 provides an overview of the relevant fuel price assumptions.

Table 2. Fuel price assumptions (2021 USD/GJ) for Europe and Africa, 2021–2050

Fuels Prices (US\$ 2021/GJ)	2021	2030	2040	2050
Biofuel/Biogas	15.28	15.28	15.28	15.28
Coal	4.58	2.00	2.03	1.88
Derived Gas	16.59	4.77	5.58	5.65
Diesel Oil	17.39	17.12	16.70	16.26
Fuel Oil	11.25	11.05	10.80	10.52
IEA Crude Oil (\$/barrel)	69.07	68.02	66.30	64.58
Lignite	3.67	1.60	1.62	1.50
Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG)	19.80	6.77	7.18	7.09
Natural Gas	18.43	5.30	6.20	6.28
Nuclear Fuel Uranium	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50
Refinery Gas	14.75	4.24	4.96	5.02
Solid Biomass	4.86	4.86	4.86	4.86

2.2.6. Capacity Factors and RES Profiles

Capacity factors (CFs) represent the ratio of actual electricity output over a given period to the theoretical maximum output if the technology operated at full capacity continuously. CFs are critical for accurately translating installed capacity into energy generation potential, especially for variable renewable energy (VRE) sources such as wind, solar, and hydropower. They determine the operational availability of technologies across time and influence investment decisions, generation patterns, and the broader reliability and cost-competitiveness of the system. Given the inherent variability of VRE resources and their geographic specificity, it is crucial to represent each country’s renewable energy resource availability and operational conditions as accurately as possible. For instance, solar PV capacity factors can vary significantly between northern and southern regions due to differences in irradiance, while wind availability is influenced by local topography, prevailing wind patterns, and proximity to coastal or high-altitude areas.

For the European countries, wind and solar PV profiles are derived from Renewables.ninja and related pre-compiled datasets [53], [54], [55], using hourly generation data based on MERRA-2 reanalysis for the year 2015, selected for its complete annual coverage and higher spatiotemporal accuracy.

For African countries, wind and solar PV profiles are also sourced from Renewables.ninja (2019) [53]. Since the platform provides data for specific geographic points rather than national averages, a scaling

procedure is applied. This involved adjusting the Ninja profiles based on national-level CFs calculated from IRENA Statistics[31] In this way, the high-resolution temporal variability from the Ninja dataset is preserved, while aligning annual generation levels with empirical observations. In cases where IRENA data is unavailable—such as for Zimbabwe and Senegal—default assumptions from the previous setup of the TEMBA model are used.

Hydropower capacity factors for Europe and Africa are computed using statistical data from IRENA Statistics [31] For each country, annual hydropower generation is compared to installed capacity, allowing the calculation of actual CFs that reflect recent operational conditions. These values are then assumed constant across the model's time horizon.

2.2.7. Temporal Resolution and Load Profiles

Temporal resolution has a significant impact on the accuracy of electricity system modelling. In both Africa and Europe, time is discretised into 16 representative time slices, defined by the combination of four seasons (December-February, March-May, June-August, September-November) and four intraday segments (UTC 00:00–07:00, 07:00–17:00, 17:00–21:00, 21:00–24:00). This common structure replaced the earlier time representations used in the models to enable consistency across regions and facilitate hard-linking capabilities. The intraday variability aims to capture peaks in electricity demand, as well as variability in renewable electricity generation.

For the European countries, hourly electricity demand profiles are derived from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform for the year 2015 [36]. This year is selected due to its full data availability and consistency. In cases where data are unavailable (e.g., for Cyprus and Malta), national sources [56] or assumptions based on system similarity are applied to construct approximate profiles. In the African context, demand profiles were sourced from the PLEXOS-World 2015 dataset [57], which provides hourly electricity load data for all countries.

2.2.8. Electricity and Gas Demand Projections

Electricity and gas demand projections in this analysis are treated as exogenous inputs. Consequently, the model does not incorporate assumptions regarding end-use technology evolution, sectoral fuel switching, electrification of final energy uses, or the impact of energy efficiency improvements. Instead, the OSeMOSYS model adopts final electricity and natural gas demand projections from corresponding TIAM-ECN scenarios specifically developed for this analysis. A recent version of the TIAM-ECN model [58] has been adjusted to adopt the same key assumptions as utilised by the OSeMOSYS model in the present analysis.

In TIAM-ECN, demand projections are derived by coupling macroeconomic drivers (e.g., GDP, population) with sectoral energy service demands, which are then met through a least-cost optimisation subject to technology availability, efficiency improvements, and policy constraints. The baseline socio-economic assumptions follow the same Shared Socioeconomic Pathway / Representative Concentration Pathway (SSP/RCP) combination used in the OSeMOSYS scenarios, ensuring alignment in long-term drivers. These projections are subsequently downscaled where needed, harmonised with the country split of the OSeMOSYS model, and adjusted for each scenario examined.

Detailed final energy demand projections for each scenario are provided in the supplementary material, while the assessed scenarios are defined in section 2.3. An overview of the final electricity and natural gas demand in each scenario can be found in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Final electricity and natural gas demand in Africa (left) and Europe (right) across scenarios for 2021, 2030, and 2050.

2.2.9. Fossil Fuels Resource Availability and Extraction Technologies

Assumptions regarding fossil fuel resource availability and extraction technologies are based on region-specific data and are treated as exogenous inputs to the model. Domestic production and reserves for natural gas are defined at a country level. The underlying data are sourced primarily from international databases [59] [60]. The relevant representation enables countries with natural gas resources to exploit domestic production within the model. Details on these assumptions can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2.10. Transmission and Distribution Losses

Transmission and distribution networks are modelled as separate aggregate technologies in each country, with associated efficiency parameters that represent system losses. These losses are implemented through time-varying efficiency values, which reflect potential improvements in network performance over the modelling horizon. This formulation enables the model to account for declining grid losses while preserving a simplified yet realistic representation of electricity delivery systems. In Europe, country-level efficiency values are based on the most recent data from the Council of European Energy Regulators (CEER) [61], with projections assumed to remain constant beyond 2022. For countries lacking data (e.g., Denmark, Luxembourg, Malta, the UK, and Italy), proxy values are adopted from comparable systems. In Africa, historical efficiencies for 2021–2023 are sourced from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) [60], while long-term projections are aligned with estimates from the JRC-TEMBA dataset [39]. Future improvements are implemented by applying the 2050 percentage reduction from the previous TEMBA values to the current EIA data, allowing for a gradual and nationally-differentiated decline in losses over the modelling horizon. Data for the transmission and distribution losses can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2.11. Capacity Reserve Margin

To ensure system adequacy over the modelling horizon, a minimum capacity reserve margin of 10–11% above the annual peak demand is imposed. To operationalize this constraint, capacity credits are assigned to each generation and storage technology, reflecting their ability to contribute reliably to

peak demand. These capacity credits are based on the technology’s availability factor, which is the fraction of installed capacity that can be expected to be reliably available during peak demand periods. Dispatchable plants (e.g., thermal units, pumped storage etc.) have high availability factors and thus higher capacity credits, while variable renewables such as wind and solar have significantly lower values reflecting their intermittency.

2.2.12. Greenhouse gas emissions and carbon markets

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are tracked through technology-specific emission factors applied to fuel combustion activities. Emissions are calculated in metric tons of CO₂ per petajoule (MtCO₂/PJ), focusing exclusively on CO₂ in line with the scope of energy-related emissions and international reporting practices. Default emission factors are based on the IPCC 2006 Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories [62] and are applied uniformly across all countries. The emission factors used in the model can be found in the supplementary material.

Carbon pricing is incorporated where applicable to reflect existing or planned carbon market mechanisms. In European countries, the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) is represented through an exogenous carbon price trajectory, expressed in USD2021/tCO₂. The adopted price path (Table 3) is derived from the latest policy guidance issued by the European Commission to EU Member States [63]. In contrast, the model does not apply carbon price across African countries, consistent with the current lack of a harmonized carbon pricing framework in the continent, despite the exception of certain countries (i.e., South Africa).

Table 3. EU ETS Price Projections adopted in each scenario branch.

Scenario (USD2021/tCO ₂)	2021	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
No CO₂ emissions	66.19	96.75	96.75	101.84	101.84	162.94	193.49
Net Zero CO₂ emissions	66.19	96.75	96.75	142.57	295.33	437.90	499.00

2.3. Scenario Framework

The analysis is structured around two main scenario categories, reflecting the presence or absence of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission targets: (i) No CO₂ Emission Targets, and (ii) Net Zero CO₂ Emissions. These categories are further disaggregated based on assumptions about energy trade, resulting in three distinct trade configurations: Limited Trade, Planned Trade, and Unrestricted Trade.

The Baseline Trade scenario reflects current trade patterns and includes only existing cross-border infrastructure for electricity and gas. The Planned Trade scenario incorporates interconnection projects that are currently under construction or officially planned. The Unrestricted Trade scenario represents an expanded system with additional candidate or proposed infrastructure, capturing long-term integration potential beyond current commitments.

In the “No CO₂ Emission Targets” category, there are no explicit constraints on CO₂ emissions, and no carbon pricing is applied outside of the EU. Within the European region, the ETS carbon price trajectory is applied as an exogenous input, following the With Existing Measures (WEM) scenario, based on recommendations by the European Commission [50]. In African countries, no carbon pricing is applied under this category.

In the “Net Zero CO₂ Emissions” category, decarbonisation in electricity supply is introduced through a linear post-processing adjustment of emissions. Specifically, electricity-sector CO₂ emissions are reduced linearly from 2030 levels, based on the corresponding “No CO₂ Emissions” scenario in each country, to zero by 2050. This approach reflects a stylized decarbonisation pathway while maintaining

comparability across countries. In the EU, the ETS carbon price follows the With Additional Measures (WAM) scenario through 2050, while no carbon pricing is assumed for African countries.

A summary of the scenario framework is presented in Table 4, detailing the configuration of carbon pricing and emission constraints across trade and climate policy dimensions.

Table 4. Scenario matrix by climate policy and energy trade assumptions.

Trade Scenario	ID	Climate Policy	EU ETS	AU ETS	Emissions Treatment
Baseline Trade	BS	No CO ₂ Emission Targets	WEM	N/A	No CO ₂ emission constraints
	BSNZ	Net Zero CO ₂ Emissions	WAM	N/A	Linear reduction of CO ₂ emissions from 2030 to 2050
Planned Trade	PN	No CO ₂ Emission Targets	WEM	N/A	No CO ₂ emission constraints
	PNNZ	Net Zero CO ₂ Emissions	WAM	N/A	Linear reduction of CO ₂ emissions from 2030 to 2050
Unrestricted Trade	UN	No CO ₂ Emission Targets	WEM	N/A	No CO ₂ emission constraints
	UNNZ	Net Zero CO ₂ Emissions	WAM	N/A	Linear reduction of CO ₂ emissions from 2030 to 2050

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Capacity and generation mix

The installed generation capacity projections across the scenarios allow for some important observations (Figure 3). Firstly, the Net-Zero variants of each of the scenarios (BSNZ, PNZ, UNZ) lead to substantially higher capacity investments compared to their alternatives without CO₂ emission targets, especially so in Africa. This is due to the need for investments in variable renewable energy technologies without a lower capacity factor than fossil-fired thermal units. Secondly, as we move from a scenario with lower interconnection capacity (i.e. BS or BSNZ) to equivalent scenarios with a higher interconnection capacity (i.e., PN & UN or PNNZ & UNNZ), the installed generation capacity is lower. This is especially noticeable in the case of Africa and the Net-Zero scenario variants; in the BSNZ total installed capacity in 2050 is 970 GW, while in the PNNZ and the UNNZ scenarios capacity reaches 753-770GW. The difference in Europe is not as pronounced as in Africa; this can be attributed to the fact that European countries are already well interconnected, which means that the planned infrastructure additions will have a lower impact on generation capacity investments.

What’s more, the capacity projections indicate differences between the two continents. In the case of Europe, most of the capacity additions related to solar PV and wind installations. In the case of Africa, solar PV and wind capacity additions are complemented with investments in hydropower and solar thermal with storage.

Figure 3. Generation capacity projections in Africa (top) and Europe (bottom) across the six scenarios.

The outlook for electricity generation is directly affected by the capacity investments. As such, the aforementioned capacity trends regarding the prominent renewable energy technologies are observed in the generation mix as well (Figure 4). However, it is important to mention that fossil-fired generation is not completely eliminated by 2050, even in the scenarios with net-zero CO₂ emission targets. This is due to the fact that there are investments in fossil-fired generation (primarily natural gas) with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) in both Africa and Europe. This fossil-fired generation with CCS is used to assist with grid stability and to provide electricity in periods where renewable energy availability is lower. Biomass with CCS is also used at lower levels in both Africa and Europe. Detailed national-level projections of capacity and generation are provided in Appendix B.

Figure 4. Electricity generation mix projections in Africa (top) and Europe (bottom) across the six scenarios.

Due to the considerable investments in variable renewable energy technologies, the need for storage increases. As indicated by Figure 5, storage capacity is projected to grow in all six scenarios in both Africa and Europe. In 2021, existing storage capacity relates primarily to pumped hydro in both continents. By 2030, negligible differences can be observed across the six scenarios, as investments are mainly limited to already planned projects; these are significantly higher in Europe. By 2050, substantial investments in battery storage can be seen; these are more pronounced in the scenarios with net-zero CO₂ emission targets. It also is interesting to note that the need for storage investments decreases as the availability of grid interconnections increases. For instance, in Africa total storage

capacity in 2050 reaches approximately 271 GW in the BSNZ scenario, while it is limited to approximately 233 and 230 GW in the PNNZ and UNNZ scenarios respectively.

Figure 5. Storage capacity projections in Africa (top) and Europe (bottom) across the six scenarios.

3.2. Electricity and natural gas trade

Cross-border energy trade is central to the integration of African and European energy systems, shaping both system flexibility and resource exchange. To illustrate these dynamics, this section presents spatial maps of net electricity and natural gas flows for the suite of assessed scenarios. The analysis focuses on the Baseline, Planned and Unrestricted Trade scenarios, with and without GHG emission targets, for the years 2030 and 2050. By comparing these maps, the evolution of trade patterns and the impact of climate constraints can be clearly observed.

Figure 6. Net electricity (left) and natural gas (right) trade flows in the BS scenario for 2030 and 2050.

Looking at the baseline scenario in Figure 6, electricity exchanges within Africa in 2030 and 2050 remain comparatively limited, with most flows concentrated within Europe and only a small number of cross-Mediterranean connections. Gas plays an important role in trade, primarily through intra-European connections, while links to Africa remain limited. By 2050, electricity exchanges intensify slightly, but the overall trade pattern remains largely unchanged.

Figure 7. Net electricity (left) and natural gas (right) trade flows in the BSNZ scenario for 2030 and 2050.

Introducing net-zero constraints in the BSNZ scenario (Figure 7) relatively alters the trade balance. By 2030, electricity flows increase modestly as renewables expand, while gas trade begins to retreat

relative to the baseline. By 2050, electricity corridors across the Mediterranean and within Africa expand somewhat, while gas remains present but in a reduced role.

EL Trade PN Scenario - 2030, Electricity

NG Trade PN Scenario - 2030, Gas

EL Trade PN Scenario - 2050, Electricity

NG Trade PN Scenario - 2050, Gas

Figure 8. Net electricity (left) and natural gas (right) trade flows in the PN scenario for 2030 and 2050.

When interconnection capacity is expanded in the PN scenario (Figure 8), the trade picture shifts noticeably. By 2030, electricity exchanges across the Mediterranean are visibly stronger than in BS, yet gas still holds a central role, particularly through North African corridors. By 2050, African and European electricity grids are more firmly integrated, with intra-African connections also strengthening, while gas shows a stronger presence compared to previous scenarios.

Figure 9. Net electricity (left) and natural gas (right) trade flows in the PNNZ scenario for 2030 and 2050.

In the PNNZ scenario (

Figure 9), the effect of interconnection expansion is amplified by the net-zero target. By 2030, electricity trade already surpasses that of PN, with stronger north–south integration, while gas begins to decline more sharply. By 2050, Africa emerges as a major renewable exporter to Europe, while gas trade is reduced compared to the PN scenario.

Figure 10. Net electricity (left) and natural gas (right) trade flows in the UN scenario for 2030 and 2050.

The unrestricted trade (UN) scenario depicted in Figure 10, enables the most rapid expansion of transmission infrastructure. Electricity exchanges in 2030 are far more extensive than in PN, supported by stronger north–south and intra-African integration. By 2050, the electricity network is the densest of all scenarios without CO₂ emission targets, while gas trade maintains a critical role in the energy system of the two continents.

Figure 11. Net electricity (left) and natural gas (right) trade flows in the UNNZ scenario for 2030 and 2050.

The UNNZ scenario (Figure 11) represents the most integrated and decarbonised future from the suite of scenarios. By 2030, electricity flows are already substantial, with Africa and Europe tightly linked, while gas flows are clearly reduced compared to UN. By 2050, electricity dominates the picture almost entirely, cementing Africa’s role as a renewable hub and reducing gas to minor supporting flows.

Taken together, these results show two clear dynamics. First, net-zero pathways consistently suppress gas trade and expand electricity flows, as renewable energy technologies become the cornerstone of the system. Second, the degree of interconnection strongly influences the pace and scale of

integration, with PN and UN scenarios highlighting how additional transmission capacity allows African renewables to play a transformative role in decarbonisation efforts. Ultimately, Africa emerges as a key renewable exporter in all net-zero cases, while gas remains relevant only where climate constraints are weaker and interconnection expansion is limited.

The total volume of electricity trade across Europe and Africa is illustrated in Figure 12; this gradually increases over time across all six scenarios. The 2050 projections indicate that as more grid interconnections become available, electricity trade increases; this is a clear indication that the demand for electricity exchange exists but is hindered by the limited capacity of existing infrastructure; this is especially true for the African continent. Additionally, the level of electricity trade increases when net-zero emission targets are implemented across all scenario variants. This can be attributed to the integration of higher shares of variable renewable energy technologies and the exchange of electricity between countries to balance supply and demand.

Trade of natural gas also increases across the model horizon in all six scenarios (Figure 12); the projected volumes include natural gas used for electricity generation but also final demand in end-use sectors of the economy (e.g., industry, services, households etc.). The Net-Zero scenarios project considerably lower volumes of gas compared to the scenario variants without CO₂ emission targets. However, it is estimated that demand for natural gas will remain strong until mid-century; this is of course directly connected to the availability of carbon removal technologies. In case, the assumed improvements in costs for CCS do not materialise, this outlook may be adversely affected.

Figure 12. Total volumes of electricity (top) and natural gas (bottom) trade across the six scenarios. This indicates the total volume of each commodity imported/exported in the sum of represented countries in the AU and EU.

3.3. Emission trajectories

Even though this analysis utilises final natural gas demand in European and African countries as a driver of natural gas trade across the two continents, since there is no explicit representation of the entire energy system, the adopted modelling framework cannot capture all of the relevant CO₂ emissions. As such, this subsection provides a comparison of only the electricity-supply related CO₂ emissions across the six scenarios.

Figure 13. Greenhouse gas emission projections in the electricity supply sector in Africa (top) and Europe (bottom) across the six scenarios.

As illustrated by Figure 13, in the absence of CO₂ emission targets, the two continents move in opposite directions in terms of emissions in the electricity supply sector. In the case of Africa, despite the substantial investments in renewable energy technologies, the projected considerable increase in final electricity demand across the continent leads to small increases in emissions compared to the present level. However, in the case of Europe, emissions decrease substantially by 2050 across all six scenarios; this can be attributed to the combined effect of two key drivers. Firstly, the assumed improvements in renewable energy, battery technology and CCS costs improve the cost-competitiveness of these options, which gradually substitute generation by conventional thermal units. Secondly, the existence of a carbon tax (i.e., Emissions Trading System) in Europe, which is assumed to gradually increase overtime, penalises the use of conventional fossil-fired generation.

Another interesting observation can be made in the case of Africa. When no CO₂ emission constraints are implemented, the positive impact of increased interconnectivity can be clearly seen. Specifically, in the BS scenario, CO₂ emissions in the electricity supply sector of Africa reach approximately 515 Mt CO₂eq in 2050. As more investments in grid interconnections are allowed, CO₂ emissions are pushed

to lower levels, reaching 430 and 406 Mt CO₂eq in the PN and UN scenarios respectively by 2050. The lower emission levels in these two scenarios can be explained by the fact that more cost-effective renewable energy resources are unlocked in remote areas of the African continent through additional investments in grid expansion.

3.4. Financial impact of scenarios

The overall system cost as extracted by the model results provides useful insights (Figure 14). One immediate observation relates to the fact that the Net-Zero variant of each of the trade scenarios results in overall higher system costs compared to the equivalent scenario without CO₂ targets. This is reasonable given that additional investments in carbon-neutral generation and storage technologies are needed to achieve decarbonisation of electricity supply. However, in the case of Europe the difference is only marginal between the two variants – this also explains why the emissions in 2050 is almost zero in all six scenarios. It should be noted that the carbon emissions cost (i.e., ETS) in Europe is higher in the Net-Zero scenarios due to the higher ETS price assumed in these scenario variants.

Figure 14. Total system cost in Africa (top) and Europe (bottom) by cost category across the six scenarios for the entire model horizon.

Furthermore, as investments in trade infrastructure increase (i.e., as we move from BS to PN and UN), the overall system cost also increases. This is because substantial capital investments are needed for this trade infrastructure. Another reason for the higher cost is that the model is forced to invest in all of the identified trade infrastructure in each scenario, instead of allowing potential investments in equivalent projects of lower capacities. As such, potential financial benefits offered by increased interconnectivity are not directly evident. Additionally, since the entire energy system is not represented, potential financial benefits offered in other sectors of the energy system by expansion of natural gas trade infrastructure are not fully captured by the modelling framework. Similarly, grid

interconnectors and gas trade infrastructure have lifetimes that exceed the model horizon; as such, their benefit may not be fully visible due to the limited temporal outlook.

To make a fairer comparison between the scenarios a secondary focus on the electricity supply sector is given. As such, the system cost components are also compared without the fuel cost for natural gas at the final demand level and without the associated capital investments for natural gas trade infrastructure (Figure 15), which provides an alternative perspective. Even though the conclusion that Net-Zero CO₂ scenarios are more expensive still stands, the overall system cost tends to decrease with additional investments in electricity trade infrastructure. This conclusion applies for the European case for scenarios without and without CO₂ emission constraints, but it is only valid for the Net-Zero CO₂ scenarios in the African case. Specifically, in Europe the system cost for PN-PNNZ and UN-UNNZ scenarios are approximately 1.3 trillion USD₂₀₂₁ lower than the BS-BSNZ scenarios. Differences in Africa for the Net-Zero CO₂ scenarios are lower, but are still substantial as they amount up to 112 billion USD₂₀₂₁.

Figure 15. Total system cost in Africa (top) and Europe (bottom) by cost category across the six scenarios for the entire model horizon, excluding final demand for natural gas and gas trade infrastructure investment costs.

4. Conclusions

The present effort has contributed to the update of available open-source energy system models of Africa and Europe. In doing so, a new model has been developed that allows analysis of energy trade potential within and between the two continents. The relevant datasets are made publicly available with this report so that they can be used and further developed by the modelling community. Additionally, the analysis has contributed to the relevant literature on energy trade and its effects on the decarbonisation effort.

The energy outlook in both Africa and Europe is projected to shift in the coming decades across all the scenarios of the present analysis. In the case of Africa, the target of achieving universal access to electricity, a fast-growing population and a decline in the costs of renewable energy technologies are the main drivers of a growth in electricity demand and subsequent investments in electricity supply infrastructure. In the case of Europe, prevailing energy and climate policies are promoting investments in renewable energy and storage technologies, which are further enabled by the push towards electrification of end-use sectors and services, such as transport, industry and space heating. The increased shares of variable renewable energy sources should be accompanied by investments in grid infrastructure. Interconnectors that improve the ability to import electricity in periods of supply shortages or export surplus electricity in peak generation periods can facilitate the integration of variable renewable energy technologies and assist with grid stability.

As countries strive to align their development plans with the Paris Agreement targets, the risk for stranded assets is quite high. As shown by the scenario outputs, a substantial share of gas trade infrastructure may continue to be significantly utilised despite the transition to higher shares of renewable energy, even in the Net-Zero CO₂ emission scenario variants. However, this is highly dependent on the successful implementation of CCS technologies and the rollout of cost-competitive technology options. In the medium-term, even in Europe, growth in natural gas demand for electricity generation is assisted by the gradual phase-out of coal- and lignite-fired power plants.

The analysis illustrates the benefits offered to decarbonisation efforts by increased electricity interconnection within and between the examined continents. However, the establishment of the relevant infrastructure is capital intensive and can be prone to significant delays, for instance due to technical, financial or political reasons. As such, in an effort to diversify the supply mix of carbon-neutral energy, other alternatives could also be examined; one notable example is that of hydrogen. Green hydrogen can be produced from renewable electricity and transported across countries via pipelines in a gaseous form or via ships in a liquified form, and can then be used to decarbonise critical sectors, such as heavy industry or freight transport. The potential for hydrogen trade between Africa and Europe can be examined in later enhancements of this effort.

Furthermore, the analysis identifies the importance of certain key corridors through which renewable electricity can flow within and between the continents. However, the adopted models do not adequately represent the national grid networks, which may pose potential limitations. Deployment of renewable energy technologies will have to be accompanied by grid investments to minimise the risk of congestion of key transmission lines. Furthermore, even though the adopted model's temporal resolution has been expanded, it is still quite low. As such, it does not capture extreme variations in renewable electricity generation nor electricity demand. Similarly, certain important technical characteristics of power plants, such as ramping rates, minimum stable operation levels and startup times are not considered, due to the computational effort that this would entail. These are of importance in terms of grid stability and merit further investigation. As such, they can be the focus of future expansions of the present modelling work.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Standardised structure of each national electricity supply system

Figure 16. Reference Energy System Africa

Figure 17. Reference Energy System Europe

Appendix B – Installed Capacity and Generation Mix by Country

Figure 18. Installed capacity mix by technology and country under the BS scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 19. Installed capacity mix by technology and country under the BSNZ scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 20. Installed capacity mix by technology and country under the PN scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 21. Installed capacity mix by technology and country under the PNNZ scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 22. Installed capacity mix by technology and country under the UN scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 23. Installed capacity mix by technology and country under the UNNZ scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 24. Electricity generation mix by technology and country under the BS scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 25. Electricity generation mix by technology and country under the BSNZ scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 26. Electricity generation mix by technology and country under the PN scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 27. Electricity generation mix by technology and country under the PNNZ scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 28. Electricity generation mix by technology and country under the UN scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

Figure 29. Electricity generation mix by technology and country under the UNNZ scenario (2021, 2030, 2050).

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